

Masrur Rock Temple Complex of Kangra, Himachal Pradesh

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Abstract

The Masrur Group of Temples, located in the Kangra Valley of Himachal Pradesh, is the only monolithic rock-cut temple complex in Northern India. Dating back to the early medieval period, this sandstone structure exhibits remarkable architectural craftsmanship and historical significance. First documented in 1875, the site suffered significant damage in the 1905 earthquake. A detailed survey was conducted in 1913 by British officials, shedding light on its architectural and cultural heritage. Local legend associates the temple with the Pandavas, who are believed to have attempted constructing a staircase to heaven, a feature that remains unfinished within the complex.

Key Words: Monolithic Rock-Cut Temple, Kangra Valley, Pandavas Legend

Introduction

Masrur group of temples is the only Monolithic Rock cut temple complex of Northern India in the Kangra valley of Beas River located in the state of Himachal Pradesh. The small hamlet of Masrur lies almost 40 Km in the south-west of Kangra town. It was first noted in 1875, as ‘The objects of antiquarian interest in the Punjab and its dependencies, Lahore, 1875’. Unfortunately, no photographs and architectural drawings have been recovered. In 1905 CE a devastating earthquake damaged considerably the temple complex. The first systematic visit of this site was occurred in 1913 by a Civilian Officer named H.L. Shuttleworth. Esq. Hoshiarpur and scientifically documented by Mr. Hargreaves, officiating Superintendent of Hindu & Buddhist Monuments, Northern Circle of Archaeological Department.’ (Indian Antiquary, 1915 p 20).

Legend is that the Pandavas stayed here for some days during their exile, Vanavaas, and the story is associated with the unfinished staircase inside the Masrur temple. The Pandavas were vowed to build a staircase to reach the heaven by the morning. After getting to know about this Debraj Indra get anxious and took the form of a crow and croaked loudly before the daybreak and there by avert them to complete the staircase. Two unfinished staircases are still a part of this Masrur rock-cut sandstone temple.

Geography

Kangra valley lies in the lap of the western Himalayas, extends from the foot of the Dhauladhar range of mountains to the south of the Beas River. The district is bounded on the North by Lahul-Spiti and Chamba, south by Hamirpur, east by Kullu and Mandi, south-west by Una and north-west by Gurudaspur of Panjab.

Kangra valley has been shaped parallel to the strike of the underlying rocks and so in geological term it is known as strike valley or longitudinal valley. Many perennial rivers flow through this valley irrigating its land.

The Making of the temple complex

It is an early 8th Century CE cruciform temple complex, and have been created out of a block of sandstone rock (hill crest) facing towards the Dhauladhar Range of Himalayan in the North Eastern side. The central part of the temple complex is 160 ft /105 ft approximately in size and surrounded by other subsidiaries shrines. Masrur temple complex was curved according to the basic features of North Indian temple architecture, laid out in a square grid place at the height about 2500 ft above the sea level. It stands as one of the most significant stone temples in the sub-Himalayan region.

In the words of H.L. Shuttleworth- “The abundance and richness of the deep-cut carvings round the doorways and on the faces of the shikharas are remarkable. Some of them are wonderfully well preserved by being to some extent protected from the weather by being overhung by projections. The high level of the execution is equalled in no other early temple in this part.” (Indian Antiquity. 1915. P21). The monolithic character may also be attributed their survival amid the devastation caused by earthquake in 1905 overtook many important ancient structures of this region. (Archaeological Report 1915-1916. P 39)

The main sanctum of the temple complex has a square plan, as do other shrines and the mandapa. Some are of opinion that this temple is an integrated monument with many shikharas with a central sanctum. Others think each shikhara represents an individual temple. In Archaeological report 1915-1916 of ASI, it has been described as ‘The centre is occupied by the principal shrine which faces a little north of east. Almost in line with this and on either side are two subsidiary shrines of decreasing size, the smaller and more distant one occupying the outer angle. A similar arrangement of these secondary shrines appears to have formed the back of the monument so that the principal temple stood in the centre of eight smaller ones, the whole hewn in the base of rectangular mass of rock, the thresholds of all shrines, therefore on one level.’ (p.42).

The main shrine now houses the images of Lord Rama, Lakshmana, and Sita, but scholars believe that the temple was originally dedicated to Lord Shiva.

Idols of Rama, Sita nd Lakshamana.

The main shrine originally has a square portico or mandapa (now lost) by climbing two steps. It is now open to the sky, supported by massive carved pillars, the remains of three of which are still to be seen, the base of one is in situ. (Annual report of Archaeological Survey of India, 1915-16, p 20). Ground plan below after H.hargreaves.

Fig: Pillared Mandapa

Fig.: Temple complex

Fig.: The cella and the garbhagriha has a large gateway lavishly carved with carvings.

The Ruchaka or Rucaka pillasters (Ruchaka pillasters is a type of Stambha mentioned in the early texts on Indian architecture) of the antarala and the mukhamandapa are richly decorated with diamond patterns, ardha-padma, paired ghata-pallva motifs inspire richly carved brackets of attractive designs.

It is not easy to explain the complex dilapidated architecture of Masroor temple complex in a day's visit, so I follow the report of more than hundred years old Archaeological Survey of India's chronicles.

Facing to the central Shrine a rectangular tank 155 feet in length and 85 feet wide, hollowed out of rock is located adjoining the temple cluster towards the Eastern site signifying the ritual and social relevance. Archaeological Report- 1915-16 of Archaeological Survey of India mentions 'Although perched almost on the hill top and apparently fed from an exceedingly small catchment area, it is reputed to contain water even in the driest seasons.' (Archaeological Report, 1915-16, page 39.). Moreover, this tank prevented the ancient structure from further damage, for it has prevented any accumulation of buildings in front of the temples.

Fig: Masrur Rock cut Temple Complex and the Sacred Tank

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Fig: View of Masrur temple from different angles.

Fig: Dilapidated parts of Masrur temple complex

Fig: View of a restored part

Fig.: Architectural fragments

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Fig.: A defaced divinity seated on lion-throne

Fig.: Defaced image of Vishnu

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Fig.: Mount of Lord Shiva, the Bull

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Fig.: Seated defaced figures of Sun God mounted on seven horses

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Fig.: Female figures

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Fig.: Images of Astalakshmi on the entrance

Fig.: Image of a couple and a standing female figure

Fig.: A Mithuna

Fig.: Defaced figures of Kartikeya

Fig: Other figures

Conclusion

The masrur temple is a unique example of Monolithic rock-cut shrine of of early North Indian architecture. It is of a type rare in Himalayan region in Indian Subcontinent. It is standing on the highest point of the hill.

Rock-cut caves are numerous in different regions of India. Only three shrines of free standing rock-cut architecture have hitherto been noted.

- 1) Shore Temples of Mamallapuram of Tamilnadu.
- 2) The shrines of Kailashnath Temple of Ellora, Maharashtra.
- 3) Hindu and Buddhist Temples of Dhamnar of Mandasaur District Of Madhya Pradesh.

We were overwhelmed and speechless with the view of its first site as it stands today. A strange feeling were not allowed us to leave this place. It was getting let in the evening. Our driver was in

hurry. It is a secluded place and far away from Kangra city. This place is not a very popular tourist destination.

Bibliography

- 1) The Indian Antiquary, A Journal of Oriental Research. VOL. XLIV- 1915. P-20.
- 2) Annual Report, 1915-16. Archaeological Survey of India. P-

